

Antifungal and Antibacterial studies from species of marine macro algae

V.Anantha Jothi¹, Dr. M.Selvi²

Assistant processor of botany and Research scholar
PG Research Department of Botany
Sri Parasakthi college for women (Autonomous), Courtallam ,
(Affiliated under Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli)
Tamil Nadu, India-627 802

Abstract

Bactericidal / Fungicidal studies were done to check the antibiotic / germicidal / eco-friendly nature of algal dyes. To complete these experiments, two potent pathogens which are of epidemic type, such as, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* were used and compared with tetracycline as standard. Macro algae are ubiquitous organisms, they inhabit almost everywhere. They are a renewable living resources which are also used as food, fee, pharmaceuticals, waste water treatment or for the industrial production of phycocolloids. Macro algae are an attractive and natural source of bioactive molecules such natural products may have potential for the management of fungal diseases in sustainable agriculture such as organic farming. Marine algae derivatives has shown promise as candidates in novel, antibacterial drug discovery. The efficacy of these compounds, their mechanism of action, applications as antibiotics, disinfectants and inhibitor of food borne pathogenic and spoilage bacteria are reviewed in this article.

KEY WORDS

Marine antibacterial, sea weeds, micro algae, pharmaceuticals, phycocolloids, germicidal, epidemic, tetracycline, disinfectants, inhibitor.

INTRODUCTION

Seaweeds are eukaryotic organisms that live in salty water in the ocean and are recognized as a potential source of bioactive natural products. Seaweeds are grouped as macrophytes based on the presence of pigments, classified as green, brown, and red. In India, diverse sea weeds grow abundantly along the coast of Tamil Nadu. Gujarat, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, Nicobar and Lakshadweep Islands, Goa, Maharashtra, Karnataka etc,... Seaweeds have been employed as a source of food, fragrance and medicine for millennium throughout the world.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling area

Tuticorin is located at 8.53N 78.36E in South India on the Gulf of Mannar, about 540 kilometres (340miles) to the south of Chennai. It receives rainfall from the north east monsoon, during summer and during winter, from the south-west monsoon. Tuticorin shores are home to rare marine flora and fauna.

- a. Vembar is a village panchayat located in the Tuticorin district of Tamil Nadu state, India. The latitude 9.081579 and longitude 78.363025 are the geo coordinates of the vembar.
- b. Koramballam is a village panchayat located in the Tuticorin district of Tamil Nadu state, India. The latitude 8.77 and longitude 78.1 are the geo coordinates of the korampallam.

MORPHOLOGICAL STUDIES

The following taxonomic citations were referred to identify the marine algae. The foremost comprehensive and authoritative classification of algae was given by F.E Fritsch (1935 &1948) in his book "The structure and reproduction of the algae" which was bases on such criteria as pigmentation types of flagella, assimilatory products, thallus structure and methods of reproduction (chapman &chapman,) (1941).

EXTRACTION OF ALGAL PIGMENTS

The powdered seaweed sample was soaked in different solvents such as, water, acetone, methanol and methanol : chloroform in the ratio of 1:2 and extracted. Then the extract was mixed with remaining solvents to form a mother solvent in the ratio 1:2 (1% Methanol and 2% Chloroform). They were kept for 12 -24 hours at room temperature. Then they were grounded well, the residue was filtered with whatman No.1 filter paper. The filtrate or pooled extract obtained was evaporated, concentrated and weighed by vacuum dessicator.

1.1. Bactericidal / fungicidal studies: (Disc diffusion method, NCCLS,1997)

Stock cultures of species such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* were maintained on broth for further use. Disc diffusion method is the simplest method to perform the sensitivity test. A sterile disc (whatman filter paper or sterile disc) 100°C was prepared in 1 hour. The disc was loaded with known volume (0.1ul) of extract of algae. Then the discs were placed on seeded agar (Nutrient agar / Potato Dextrose agar) plates, that were uniformly swabbed with pathogens. The control disc (Tetracycline-10 mcg/disc) was also placed in the center of the plate. Then the plates were incubated at 37° c for 24 hours. The test organism grew on the agar plate except the clear zone around the antibiotic disc, which inhibited the / extracts, which showed inhibition against the tested pathogens. After incubation the results were observed and tabulated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological observation

Ulva lactuca Linn.

Ulva lactuca is a thin flat green algae growing from a discoid holdfast. The margin is somewhat ruffled and often torn. It may reach 18 centimetres (7.1) or more in length, though generally much less, and up to 30 centimetres (12in) across. The membrane is two cells thick, soft and translucent, and grows attached, without a stipe, to rocks or other algae by a small disc shaped holdfast. Green to dark green in colour, this species in the chlorophyta is formed of two layers of cells irregularly arranged, as seen in cross-section. The chloroplast is cup-shaped in some references but as a parietal plate in others with one to three pyrenoids. There are other species of *Ulva* which are similar and not always easy to differentiate. When dried by the sun the colour of the seaweed can range from white to black.

Ulva reticulata Forsskal

Mature thalli of *ulva reticulata* have irregular shapes, light to dark green in colour, forming masses of perforated blades from a few centimetre in size to about a metre across juveniles usually attached with a small discoid holdfast becoming detached into free living individuals that could be entangled with other seaweeds, sea grasses, rocks or corals. Cross section of blade will show the blade consisting of cells which are squarish, rectangular to polygonal in shape, uninucleate containing a single parietal chloroplast with one to several pyrenoids. *Ulva reticulata* has reproduction occurring in small patches in the middle of blades which are two cells thick. During or after spore release these patches fall out blade leaving a small hole. Three holes become larger to form the characteristic pattern of holes in the blades.

Caulerpa racemosa (Forsk.)

Plants in larger and smaller groups, conspicuous. Rhizome, creeping, cylindrical, simple or divided and highly branched forming an intricate system. Rhizoids, from lower parts of prostrate rhizome, attaching plants to silt-covered stones, coral rocks and coralline pieces. Erect branches from upper sides of rhizome, irregularly scattered, 2-5 cm long or more, generally simple, terete, filiform and of uniform thickness, naked at base, higher up set up with ramuli. Central cavity of thallus with cylindrical skeletal strands, traversing in all parts, more strongly in rhizome, forming a radial system, and knotted in centre. Substance cartilaginous in stem; in ramuli, thin and membranous and flexible. Alga on drying adheres poorly to paper.

***Padina Gymnospora* (kutzing)**

Thalli attached by a small stupose rhizoidal base, are to 6.5 cm high, flabellate and composed of several lobes with enrolled margins. The superior surface is slightly to moderately calcified. Thalli are olive-brown in colour. In transverse section the thallus is composed of 4-6 layers of cells in the mid-regions and up to 8-9 layers near the base. Hair rows are present on both sides of the thallus. Tetrasporangia are arranged in concentric lines above each hair row, mainly developed on the superior surface.

Bactericidal / Fungicidal studies were done to check the antibiotic / germicidal / eco-friendly nature of algal dyes. To complete these experiments, two potent pathogens of epidemic type, such as, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* were obtained from Department of Microbiology, Sri Paramakalyani Collage, Alwarkurichi. The organisms were maintained in broth / slants for further use. Disc diffusion method is the simplest method to perform the sensitivity test. 10 mcg/disc of acetone and extracts (*U.lactuca*, *U.reticulata*, *C.racemosa* and *P.gymnospora*) were treated against agar cultures of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*. The control disc (Tetracycline-10 mcg/disc) was also placed in the center of the plate. The zone of inhibition was observed at the concentration of (0.1ul) extract (Stock Conc. 100mg/ml) where, the test controls were *C.racemosa* and *P.gymnospora* and the positive controls were the acetone and tetracycline (**Table :2**) The zone of inhibition was found in the gradation of ascending pattern of data when compared with the standard (tetracycline) antibiotic disc (**Plate: 1&2**).

U.lactuca* and *U.reticulata

- *Staphylococcus aureus* : 2≤3 9≤15 (mm) diameter
- *Candida albicans* : 8≤7 8≤18 (mm) diameter.

C.racemosa* and *P.gymnospora

- *Staphylococcus aureus* : 6≤5 9≤15 (mm) diameter
- *Candida albicans* : 4≤3 8≤18 (mm) diameter.

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \frac{\text{zone of inhibition(mm) diameter}}{\text{Maximum zone of inhibition (mm) diameter} \times 100}$$

The observed values showed that *Staphylococcus aureus* were more susceptible to test control and positive control (**Fig:1**) and *Candida albicans* was less susceptible to all the four extracts. These results conclude as, the marine algae are the good source of natural dye and also eco-friendly nature to the society.

Similar reports were in conformity with the previous reports such as, Karthikadeve et.al., (2009) who studied that the antibacterial activity of some commonly occurring green algae *Codium adherens*, *U.reticulata* and *Halimeda tuna*. The maximum antibacterial activity was noted in ethanol extract of *Ulva* against *Staphylococcus* (13mm of inhibition zone) and the minimum antibacterial activity was recorded in methanol extract of *Codium* against *Escherichia* (3mm). Kolanjinathan and Stella (2011) reported that comparative studies on antimicrobial activity of *U.reticulata* and *U.lactuca* solvent were against human pathogens and fungi. Two were extracted using organic solvents viz. Methanol, acetone, chloroform, hexane and ethyl acetate. Antimicrobial activity of *U.reticulata* and *U.lactuca* solvent extract showed maximum inhibitory activity than other having traditional claims of effectiveness might warrant fruitful result, These plants could serve as useful source of new antimicrobial agents. **Manjula and Narasimha Rao (2014)** observed that the present study was carried out to investigate its antimicrobial potentiality of the algae such as *Caulerpa racemosa* (C.Agradh.) which were studied against both gram-positive, gram negative and fungal pathogens. The zone of inhibition which was measured for all the crude extracts revealed a wide range of antimicrobial activity against tested pathogens. The overall antimicrobial activity assessed from the above results indicated the presence of active in the extractions of seaweeds which can be exploited for the production of lead molecules which are of use in pharmaceutical industry.

Fig-1. Map of sampling area Tuticorin
Ref: Satellite Pictures, <http://www.google.com>

Plate:1.Sampling area-Vembar and Korampallam at Tuticorin (A&B)

Plate :2. Habit of A. *Ulva lactuca* Linn, 1753 B.
Ulva reticulata Forsskal,1775,
C. *Caulerpa racemosa* (Forsskal) J.Agardh,1873 &
D, *Padina gymnospora* (Kutzing) Sonder, 1871.

Name of the sample	Group	Parts Used	Nature of usage	Locality in Tuticorin
<i>Ulva lactuca</i> Linn, 1753	Chlorophyceae	Whole plant	Shade dried powder	Vembar
<i>Ulva reticulata</i> Forsskal, 1775	Chlorophyceae	Whole plant	Shade dried powder	Vembar
<i>Coulerpa racemosa</i> (Forsskal), J.Agardh, 1873	Chlorophyceae	Whole plant	Shade dried powder	Vembar
<i>Padina gymnospora</i> (Kutz) Sonder, 1871	Phaeophyceae	Whole plant	Shade dried powder	Korampallam

Name of the microbes	Zone of Inhibition (mm) diameter / 0.1 ul) Acetone/Disc diffusion method extract %used (stock Cone. 100mg/ml)					
	Ulva lactuca	Ulva reticulata	Caulerpa racemosa	Padina gymnospora	Postive Control	
					Acetone	Tetra cycline
Staphylococcus aureus	11%	17%	33%	28%	50%	100%
Candida albicans	44%	38%	22%	17%	44%	100%

Fig.1 Bactericidal/ fungicidal activity of four macro algal extracts.

Plate:1. Antifungal / Antibacterial studies of natural dye obtained from *Caulerpa racemosa*

C-CONTROL, AC- Acetone extract + *C- racemosa* and T- Tetracycline

Plate:2. Antifungal (A)/ Antibacterial (B) studies on natural dye obtained from *Ulva reticulata*

C-CONTROL, AC- Acetone extract + *C- racemosa* and T- Tetracycline

SUMMARY

Bactericidal / Fungicidal studies were done to check the antibiotic / germicidal / eco-friendly nature of algal dyes. The zone of inhibition was found in the gradation of ascending pattern of data when compared with standard (tetracycline) antibiotic disc. The observed values showed that *Staphylococcus aureus* was more susceptible to test control and positive control and *Candida albicans* was less susceptible to all the four extracts. These results conclude as, the marine algae are the good source of natural dye and also eco-friendly nature to the society.

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